

Studies in Ion-exchange Equilibria. Part I. Exchange of Univalent Cations on Resins of Various Types

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The equilibrium studies have been made on different types of cation exchangers in hydrogen form with univalent alkali metal ions. It has been concluded that the apparent equilibrium constant (K_a) varies irregularly with the concentration of the external solution and hence with the equivalent fraction of the ion in the resin phase (X_{BR}) in all the cases. The shape of the curves for plots of K_a versus X_{BR} differs from resin to resin, leading to different maxima in different cases.

Ion-exchange equilibria studies using mass action concept have been made by many workers¹⁻⁴. The equilibrium constant, K , given by the relationship

$$K = \frac{a_{BR}}{a_{AR}} \cdot \frac{a_{AW}}{a_{BW}}$$

for the exchange reaction

has been shown by some workers¹⁻³ to be constant. But all of them have calculated K by using different suppositions for activities of different ions in resin phase. Boyd *et al.*¹ have used molar fractions instead of activities considering the solid phase as an ideal solution phase; Bauman and Eichhorn² have used molar concentrations for the same. Kressman and Kitchener³ have used equivalent fractions of different ions in the resin phase and only concentrations of ions in the solution phase for activities. Yet all of them have shown K to be constant. But Duncan and Lister⁴ using Dowex-50 have shown for Na^+ , Ba^{2+} , and La^{3+} ions that K varies with X_{BR} , the required fraction of ion in the resin phase. Lowen *et al.*⁵ and Reichenberg *et al.*⁶ have also confirmed this fact. But it is important to note that different workers have used different resins as well as different concentration ranges in the solution phase to reach their conclusions. This has created confusion and hence similar investigations with different types of resins (commercially available or otherwise) under varying conditions are needed to reach definite conclusions.

The present studies have been made to show the variability of K with solution concentration and equivalent fraction of the ion in resin phase (X_{BR}) for univalent alkali metal ions on some Amberlites (IR-120, IRC-50, IR-112), sulphonated coal, and a phenol

1. Boyd *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 2818.
2. Bauman and Eichhorn, *ibid.*, 1947, 69, 2830.
3. Kressman and Kitchener, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1190.
4. Duncan and Lister, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1949, 7, 104; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 3285.
5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 2066.
6. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 493.

sulphonate resin in hydrogen forms in aqueous media. Wide ranges of concentrations of ions have been used in the external solution to justify the conclusions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The resins (in hydrogen form) used in these studies included the following:—

1. Amberlite IR-120, a strongly acidic nuclear sulphonic acid type cation exchanger.
2. Amberlite IRC-50, a weakly acidic polymethacrylic acid-based carboxylic type cation exchanger.
3. Amberlite IR-112, a porous, sulphonic acid type, strongly acidic cation exchanger.
4. Sulphonated coal, a sulphonated carbonaceous cation exchanger, prepared from semi-bituminous Indian coal according to the method of Bafna *et al.*⁷
5. Sulphonated phenol formaldehyde resin, a phenolic type cation exchanger, prepared according to the procedure used by Kressman and Kitchener⁸.

The stock solutions for cationic equilibrium studies were prepared from the chlorides of lithium, sodium, potassium, rubidium, and caesium (B.D.H. AnalaR reagents) in ion-free water. In one case (resin Amberlite IR-120) a solution of ammonium chloride of the same quality was also used. Different concentrations were prepared by proper dilution of stock solutions with ion-free water.

Procedure.—The batch technique was used for equilibrium studies at room temperature ($\sim 32^\circ$). Each time 100 ml of the solution of a particular strength containing the cation under consideration was equilibrated with a known weight (1 g.) of the resin in fully swollen state (to avoid uptake of water during exchange). The reaction vessels were shaken intermittently to keep the solid and liquid phases well in contact with each other. These were kept as such until equilibrium was attained (one day for all strongly acidic exchangers and seven days for weakly acidic ones). After equilibration, aliquots were drawn from the solutions and titrated for acidity generated due to exchange of cations with hydrogen ion of the resin phase. Here it may be pointed out that the molecular sorption of the electrolyte itself, which might be there, will not affect the equilibrium coefficient⁵. Hence the liberated acidity can be taken as a measure of the concentration of H^+ ion exchanged with the cation concerned.

Such experiments were carried out over a wide range of concentrations of the exchanging ions in the external solutions (from M to $M/100$).

The limiting exchange capacities of the resins were determined by the method of Heyman and O'Donnell⁹.

Knowing these values experimentally in each case, K_a , the equilibrium constants, under stoichiometric conditions were calculated by using the expression:

$$K = \frac{X_{B_2}}{X_{A_2}} \cdot \frac{C_{A_w}}{C_{B_w}}$$

7. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1952, 11B, 134.

8. Bauman and Argensinger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 1130.

9. *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1949, 4, 395.

similar to one used by Kressman and Kitchener³ for univalent cations. Here X_{B_R} and X_{A_R} are the equivalent fractions of the ions concerned in resin phase, while C_{A_W} and C_{B_W} are the ion concentrations in solution phase.

The graphs were plotted for K_a versus X_{B_R} for each ion under study in all the cases of exchangers (see Figs. 1 to 5). To show the comparative shift in variation of K_a with X_{B_R} , similar curves for only Na^+ were also plotted (see Figs. 6 to 7) taking the values from all the resins.

FIG. 1. Amberlite IRC-50 (H).

FIG. 2. Amberlite IR.-112 (H).

FIG. 3. Amberlite IR-120 (H).

FIG. 4. Phenol sulphate (H).

DISCUSSION

The relative affinities of different ions depend on several factors, namely, the total ion concentration in the resin phase, the size of the ion concerned, the valency or the

charge of the ion concerned, the concentration of the external solution, and the type of the solvent used¹⁰. But if one uses ions of the same valency in a particular solvent and exchanges them on a particular resin, then the affinity changes are due chiefly to changes in the concentration of the external solution. The stoichiometric equilibrium constant for an exchange reaction, which is a measure of the relative affinity of an ion, is thus dependent on the changes in the concentration of the external solution. One of the reasons for conflicting values reported by different workers for ' K ' for any particular ion combination is due to the use of different exchangers. Another important reason is that they have worked within different ranges of the concentration of the external solutions.

FIG. 5. Sulphonated coal (H).

Our graphs for K_B versus X_{B_2} for all the resins very clearly indicate that stoichiometric equilibrium constant of ion-exchange reactions is not a constant quantity, but varies with the equivalent fraction of the exchanging ion in the resin phase (*i.e.* X_{B_2}). As X_{B_2} depends on the concentration of the external solution (resin weight being constant), the K_B varies with the concentration of the external solution. Figs. 1 to 5 indicate that this variation of K_B is irregular. Thus our observations for the five different types of resins (namely, strongly acidic nuclear sulphonic acid type Amberlite IR-120, weakly acidic polymethacrylic acid-based carboxylic type Amberlite IRC-50, porous sulphonic acid type Amberlite IR-112, sulphonated carbonaceous type sulphonated coal, and sulphonated phenolic type phenol-formaldehyde resin) support the observations of Duncan and Lister⁴, Lowen⁵, and Reichenberg.⁶ The above workers¹⁻³, who have shown K as constant, appear to be in error. This may be due to their use of small ranges of concentrations of the external solutions. In the case of Amberlite IR-120(H), the ranges over which exchanges have been studied are: $0.12 < X_{K_2} < 0.94$, $0.125 < X_{(NH_4)_2} < 0.968$, $0.135 < X_{Na_2} < 0.993$, $0.14 < X_{Cs_2} < 0.995$, $0.057 < X_{Li_2} < 0.61$, and $0.092 < X_{Na_2} < 0.71$. The ranges in other cases are not so wide; still their graphs indicate the trend very well.

10. Kunin, "Ion Exchange Resins", John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1958, p. 32.

Figs. 6 and 7 give a comparative idea about this variation of 'K' for only Na^+ on different resins. It is quite clear from these graphs that the maxima do not correspond to the

FIG. 6. $\text{Na}^+ - \text{H}^+$ exchange.

FIG. 7. $\text{Na}^+ - \text{H}^+$ exchange.

same value of X_{BR} in different resins. Thus, it may be concluded that K_a is never constant; but if at all it is needed to be referred to as constant for any affinity relationship, it should be mentioned together with these variables.

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Received September 2, 1961.